

Ecosomatic Mutants: Calling for a New Paradigm of Ecological Transformation in a More-than-Human World

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Abstract

This article explores the role of *ecosomatic practices* as gateways to embodied knowledge, interspecies alliances, and new forms of perception, care, and participation. If we want liveable futures, we must co-create a paradigm that reintegrates human life within a more-than-human world. In the 1970s Thomas Hanna described the “second wave” of somatics as a force of translucent egoism, predicting that individuals, no longer threatened by nature, would balance rational-assimilative and sensual-accommodative drives in a technologically shaped environment. That prediction failed. Nature did not become irrelevant — it became *vulnerable*. Ecosomatics, as the *third wave of somatics*, responds to this vulnerability and to the cultural shadows of romanticism and colonial projection. It calls for embodied participation that confronts limit, transforms grief into ecological responsiveness, and cultivates regenerative cultures of knowledge exchange.

1. Introduction

This article is based on the keynote address delivered at the *Genius Loci Symposium of Ecosomatic Arts*¹. The symposium gave voice to a wide range of perspectives — artists, scholars, educators, therapists and activists — each responding to the shared urgency: *How can we imagine and embody new paradigms of ecological transformation in a world that is more-than-human?*

The symposium was not only a gathering of presentations. It also functioned as a laboratory for sensing, listening, and participating in what was described as ecosomatic mutation. To become an *ecosomatic mutants* does not only mean allowing bodies, perceptions, and practices to recalibrate in relation to the living landscapes around and within us — human and non-human, visible and invisible, damaged and resilient. It also means building new alliances between bodies, places, and communities to address the pressing social and ecological crises of our time.

2. From Ecological Crisis to Crisis of Perception

We know the facts of ecological devastation: climate emergency, deforestation, mass extinction—just to name some of them. But scientific knowledge alone does not move us.

¹ The Symposium took place on 18–19 September at Spazio Rossellini in Rome, the multidisciplinary hub for the arts of the Lazio Region. The 2025 edition focused on the connections between bodies, places, and communities. For more info:

The deeper crisis we face is a crisis of perception. We struggle to feel and respond collectively to what we already know. Global capitalism and the technical apparatus we have built reduce us to functionaries of efficiency and consumption. In this system, human beings are no longer subjects struggling to shape their destiny; we are instruments of a technical apparatus with no end beyond its own growth.

Ecosomatic practices intervene precisely here. They awaken perception. They reconnect us with the reciprocity of sensing, caring, participating. They resist anaesthetisation. They help us feel the wounds of the world — and feeling is the beginning of transformation.

3. Looking Back – Thomas Hanna and “Translucent Egoism”

In the 1970s, philosopher and Feldenkrais practitioner Thomas Hanna described somatics as the expression of a radically new way of perceiving.² He called the “second wave” of somatics in the 1960s a transformative force working through what he named *translucent egoism*. Let me quote his words:

“The powerful and perceptive eye of the soma is there, hidden and overlaid with all manner of late-developed assimilative paraphernalia, and this somatic eye will become able to see only to the extent that the fear-aggression paraphernalia diminishes and becomes more translucent. ... A sensual-accommodative mode of experiencing is the attainment of what I would call *translucent egoism*.” (Hanna, *Bodies in Revolt*, p. 246, italics added)

For Hanna, somatics was part of a broader cultural phenomenon of “embodied liberation” in the 1960s: a radically new *conscious* approach to the environment, no longer guided by constrictive rationality, but by sensuous accommodation. He defined this drive as:

“The sensual-accommodative experience will be the most obvious thing to come to the fore when this surrender takes place; and it will come to the fore in terms of somatic relaxation—a streaming, unfocused sensuality which allows one’s somatic being to be felt by, perceived by, and molded by some aspect of one’s environment.” (p. 236)

Hanna observed that for centuries, especially in the West, humans had emphasised the assimilative drive—fear-aggression, control, and domination of the environment. But in the 1960s, the sensual-accommodative drive was reawakening to fulfill an evolutionary process. He predicted a cultural balance:

“But, because human somas have for so long—and particularly during the past three centuries within the West—maintained an unbalanced emphasis upon a fear-aggression, assimilative adaptation with their environment, the energizing of the sensual-accommodative avenues of expression will become such a dominant adaptational priority during the coming generations that this

² The discussion which follows is based on Hanna’s *Bodies in Revolt*, published in 1970, esp. Section 3, pp. 225-250, *The Third Eye*, Freeperson Press.

development will initially *seem* to be a total mutation into sensual accommodation.” (p. 237, italics in original)

In other words, Hanna expected that the *mutation of the 1960s*—the explosion of sensuous-accommodative expression—would, in time, be balanced out. That it would give rise to a new culture where the assimilative and accommodative drives would find equilibrium.

But this did not happen. The problem with his prediction was, in my opinion, to assume that nature, once safely subsumed within technological dominion and “no longer a threat,” would provide humans with the fertile reference to develop a cultural balance between assimilation and accommodation. But technological dominion did not open space for balance. It polarised the tension even further. Nature did not become a mediator between human drives. Nature became *vulnerable*.

And here lies the contradiction: accommodation requires nature to be there, holding the space for us. Hanna’s equation collapses in a world where nature itself no longer provides a stable reference. So, the question becomes: *what is the balance between rational assimilation and sensuous accommodation in a world where nature is fragile, wounded, disappearing?* Without a living environment to mirror and limit us, the balance collapses.

We need a different mutation than the one Hanna imagined. Not only to adapt to the technological environment, but to defend and repair—to save ourselves and other beings from our own technologies. From translucent egoism, we must move toward *embodied ecologies and ecological embodiment*.

4. Ecosomatics as the Third Wave of Somatics

Let us now situate ecosomatics as the *third wave* of somatics. The *first wave*, in early 20th-century Europe, arose in response to the alienation of industrial modernity. Think of pioneers like Elsa Gindler or Moshe Feldenkrais, searching for ways to recover the sensing body in an age of machines. The *second wave*, in the 1960s—especially in the United States—emerged as part of cultural liberation, the counterculture, the quest for embodied awareness and personal freedom. As Hanna put it:

“The twentieth-century awakening to a quest for ‘meaning’ is the awakening of the repressed and sleeping portion of our somas to the task of adaptation. The ‘dark,’ ‘irrational,’ sensual-accommodative drives have begun to lurch and deploy their forces, and, in consequence, men have been uncannily disturbed, not really being able to consciously pinpoint or understand the nature of this strange malaise.” (p. 235)

And now, the *third wave* of ecosomatics, from the early 2000s onward, responds to something else: planetary vulnerability. Not industrial alienation. Not only cultural liberation. But the fragility of the living systems that sustain us. Ecosomatics proposes transformation not by assimilating the world through domination, nor by romantically accommodating to it, but by re-entering the field of *interspecies alliances*.

By recognising that our soma is porous, entangled, inseparable from the more-than-human and by working actively to repair the connective tissues between bodies, places and communities. To be ecosomatic today is to become a mutant. Not a mutant of domination. Not a mutant of accommodation. But a mutant of reciprocity.

5. Challenges and Shadows

But let us also be clear about the challenges. Ecosomatics can sometimes *romanticise nature*, or project colonial fantasies onto Indigenous cosmologies. Reciprocity is not always harmony: it includes conflict, tension, and asymmetry. Another challenge is *individualism*. Somatic work has often focused on personal liberation. But in the face of ecological crises, what we need is not only individual freedom but collective responsiveness. Ecosomatics must become a practice of commoning: cultivating embodied participation that generates community — human and more-than-human, adaptive and transformable.

Ecosomatic practice and philosophy — and the return to nature that a growing number of artists, researchers, educators and therapists are exploring and promoting — tend to be still embedded, with (more or less) awareness, within colonial paradigms. In ecosomatics we often take for granted the “ecological” connection of body and environment as extensions of each other (as an experience or a hope) and the “somatic” connection of mind, body and spirit as an integral being. Yet little critical work has examined the cultural, political, and epistemological contexts from which we make these assumptions, and the influence of non-Western cultures in shaping them.

The return to the body and nature is often pursued as or through a projection of non-Western “premodern” models of oneness with nature, which practitioners cling to while failing to surrender the very relation of dominion over nature that underpins ecosomatic discourse itself. Examples include *Bodyweather* stemming from Butoh in Japan, the practice of Suprpto Suryadarmo in Indonesia, Aboriginal Dreamtime philosophy in Australia, Native American economies of gift and reciprocity, and Amerindian cosmologies across South America.³

As Elise Nuding (2021) warns, ecosomatics is not automatically emancipatory simply because it combines soma and ecology. There is a risk of reproducing romanticised or modern-colonial concepts of “nature” as external other, or of assuming that discourses of entanglement, posthumanism, and inclusivity automatically ensure accountability in practice. The challenge is to ask: what do practitioners actually do, and how do practices mobilise discourse in concrete encounters between humans and forests?

I propose embodied participation as the operative principle through which ecosomatics itself must be critically re-examined. Participation, framed as embodied inquiry, anchors ecosomatics in a methodology of critical accountability, ensuring that practices are not only discursively innovative but also materially transformative. This situates ecosomatics as a transdisciplinary methodology and ecological practice, advancing the field while holding it

³ For recent collections of ecosomatic work, mainly from Europe, the US, Australia, and Canada, see: Fraleigh, S. and Riley, S.R. (eds.), 2024. *Geographies of Us*; and the double special issue of the *Journal of Dance and Somatic Practices* on ‘Embodying Eco-Consciousness’, edited by Kampe, McHugh and Munker (2021).

accountable to the communities and environments with which it engages. Yet, to deepen this accountability, we also need to examine the cultural foundations of Western thought itself. Ecosomatics is not created in a vacuum: it inherits philosophical legacies that continue to shape our ways of perceiving nature, body, and participation. Among these legacies, the Greeks occupy a key and paradoxical place — at once amongst Europe’s “own colonisers” and the originators of concepts that still structure Western culture. Their myths and tragedies not only prefigured the performing arts, but also embodied a paradigm of transformative participation that continues to resonate today.

6. The Greek Legacy for Staying with the Trouble

I want to borrow Donna Haraway’s expression *staying with the trouble* (2016) to suggest that ecosomatics must not flee into romanticised returns to nature or borrowed cosmologies, but rather cultivate the capacity to remain with the tensions, contradictions, and troubles of our own cultural inheritances. Turning to our Greek legacy—as Italians, Europeans, as Westerners, but more in general as human beings—can be an effective move.

When we speak of our technologically driven, globalised, market-based civilisation, we are describing an order that has emerged from modern science and humanism, rooted in a Christian paradigm that conceives of nature as a field for human dominion—in today’s words, as a reservoir of extractable raw materials. Italian philosopher of history and psychoanalyst Umberto Galimberti (2021) reminds us that this positioning of nature is not timeless: it marks a historical shift. For the Greeks, nature was not a resource to be mastered but an immutable reference, a mirror of necessity (*Ananke*) that set limits on human action.

The ancient Greeks recognised the dangers of calculative rationality and technological advancement through myth and tragedy, embedding the story of Prometheus into the cultural fabric of collective performance. Prometheus, A titan punished by the gods for giving humans the gift of rationality and technique, was chained to a mountain, condemned to have his liver eaten daily by an eagle, only for it to regenerate each night. In this myth, *techne* was inseparable from danger and bound to the law of necessity. Modern humans, by contrast, have unchained Prometheus. We inhabit what Galimberti calls the *Age of Techne*, in which calculative rationality makes everything possible while eroding the foundations of ethics. Ethics, he argues, becomes “pathetic” when no longer grounded in necessity or in a shared reference point.

The second aspect of the Greek legacy that is relevant to a critical and participatory ecosomatics is the *Dionysian impulse*, as described by Nietzsche in *The Birth of Tragedy*. For Nietzsche (2008), Greek culture balanced Apollonian aesthetic form with Dionysian surrender to the aliveness of nature. With the rise of Christianity, this balance was destroyed. The death of Pan — the god of wild nature — marked the exclusion of the Dionysian from Western consciousness and the redefinition of nature as a field of dominion, while death itself was reframed as something to be overcome through divine redemption. Thomas Hanna drew on Nietzsche when discussing somatic sensuous accommodation, seeing in it a mutation towards a more embodied relation with the world:

“In sensual-accommodative experience we perceive in a radically different manner because it involves behaving in this same manner; it involves immediate, unself-conscious somatic surrender to drive patterns evoked by the situation. And it is, itself, pure expression: a letting-the-soma-loose in its emetic response to its environment. In its purity, it is what Nietzsche called the Dionysian expression; in its disciplined, fulfilled form which will come during the next century, it is what Nietzsche called Dionysian-Apollonian expression.” (Hanna, 1970, p. 242)

Hanna predicted that sensuous accommodation would counterbalance rational assimilation. Yet his forecast collapsed. Where nature ceases to provide the stable reference for such balance, the Dionysian no longer mediates human drives; it survives only as a reminder of what has been excluded.

To re-engage the Dionysian today is to engage with the deep ethical and ontological implications of limit. Greek tragedy, born from the rituals for Dionysus, transformed myth into performance and established the precursor of Western theatre and performing arts. It was not only storytelling, but participatory practice: tragedies staged conflicts between individual desire, the laws of the *polis*, and the demands of the gods. They embodied necessity in collective form. For ecosomatics, this legacy is vital. It suggests that embodied practices must confront limit, conflict, and interdependence rather than bypass them through romanticism or technological illusion.

To “stay with the trouble” in ecosomatics is to refuse both nostalgia for lost unity and projections of harmony onto other cultures. It means cultivating the Dionysian impulse and expression as a paradigm of embodied limit and tragic participation — one of the few inheritances in Western culture that still offers a way to perceive and enact interdependence with the more-than-human world.

7. From Mutation to a New Paradigm of Ecological Transformation

When I call for a new paradigm of ecological transformation, I mean a new framework for *embodied participation*. A paradigm is not only a theory. It is a shared language, a model for acting together, sharing assumptions about how the world works.

Hanna’s foreseen paradigm of balance between assimilation and accommodation never materialised, because nature became vulnerable. Without it, balance cannot emerge. Ecosomatics must therefore seed a different paradigm: one that begins from vulnerability, grief, and reciprocity. Ecosomatics can provide experiences where perception shifts, grief is felt, care enacted, creation made collaborative, and alliances formed. It must be a paradigm of ecological embodiment and embodied ecologism. Not assimilation. Not accommodation. But transformation through alliance, interdependence, and embodied participation in the more-than-human world. Transformation here does not mean sudden revolution. It means transitions: small shifts, everyday practices, collective experiments that accumulate into cultural change.

8. Toward a Culture of Regeneration

How can ecosomatics move from a multidisciplinary field to a transdisciplinary phenomenon? By transforming the culture of knowledge exchange itself. Research is not only about transmitting facts. It is about generating relationships.

At the heart of the *Genius Loci* Symposium lied not only the sharing of research and artistic practice, but also the way we listen, respond, and participate. Ecological crises are also crises of perception and participation: the way we relate to each other reflects the way we relate to the more-than-human world. If ecosomatic practice teaches us to attune body and environment, it can also teach us to regenerate the culture of exchange among humans — integrating debate and confrontation with embodied participation, reciprocity, and generative dialogue. This is an invitation to experiment with a regenerative paradigm of feedback and questioning, one that nourishes processes of creation, research, and collective awareness. Giving and receiving feedback is thus not limited to an evaluative moment but becomes a shared practice of perception, care, and alliance-building. This approach was articulated in the framework “Practicing Regenerative Feedback: A Framework for Participation and Exchange,” which was shared with *Genius Loci* participants and can serve as inspiration for other contexts of knowledge sharing (Rufo, 2025).

9. Conclusion and Call to Action

Ecosomatics, as the third wave of somatics, calls us to move from translucent egoism to embodied ecologies and ecological embodiment. Ecosomatic mutants are not superheroes or hermits. They are humans experimenting with new forms of being-together — artists, scholars, educators, citizens.

Let us weave our voices, practices, and imaginaries into a culture of regeneration. Let us begin the work of embodying the more-than-human world.

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